

Finding Minimal Units In Several Two-Fold Fuzzy Finite

Neutrosophic Rings

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have defined the concept of minimal units in finite two-fold fuzzy neutrosophic rings modulo integers as a generalization of classical elements of the group of units of the mentioned neutrosophic rings. We apply our results to characterize all minimal units in the following two-fold neutrosophic rings $(Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ for $n \in \{2,3,4,5\}$.

Keywords: two-fold algebra, finite neutrosophic ring, modulo integer ring, minimal unit.

Introduction

The determination of the invertible elements in a ring has attracted the attention of many researchers, specifically in some modern rings such as neutrosophic rings, and n-cyclic refined neutrosophic rings [6-8]. Many interesting results have been proved about the problem of classifying the group of units in a number of special solutions, and also tables that calculate the value of these units and determine their exact number [9-10].

A unit in a ring R is the concept of being an invertible element concerning multiplication operation which make a group together.

Two-fold neutrosophic algebras are new algebraic structures presented by Smarandache [1] by combining neutrosophic values of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy with classical algebraic sets. These ideas were used by many authors to generalize other famous algebraic structures such as two-fold fuzzy number theoretical systems [2-3], two-fold modules and spaces [4], and two-fold fuzzy rings [5]. Also, they were used in the study of some special two-fold complex functions such as Gamma function [13], and in extending n-refined neutrosophic rings [11-15]. The complex fuzzy ring initiated on complex fuzzy space was given by Al-Husban [14-17]

In this work, we define the minimal two-fold neutrosophic finite ring modulo integers, and we determine all maximal units in these rings for the special values of n between 2 and 5. We have also classified all the units that have been calculated in tables showing their values as well as their number.

Main Discussion

Definition 2.1.

Let $Z_n = \{0,1, \dots, n - 1\}$ be the ring of integers modulo n, and $Z_n(I) = \{a + bI \ ; \ a, b \in Z_n \ , I^2 = I \}$ be the corresponding neutrosophic ring. Assume that $f: Z_n \rightarrow [0,1]$ be a fuzzy mapping with

$$\begin{cases} f(0) = 0 \\ f(1) = 1 \end{cases} \ ; \ f_I: Z_n(I) \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ such that:}$$

$$f_I(a + bI) = \min(f(a), f(b)).$$

The minimal two-fold neutrosophic ring $(Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ is defined as:

$$(Z_n(I))_{f_I} = \{(a + bI)_{f_I(c+dI)} \ ; \ a + bI, c + dI \in Z_n(I)\}.$$

Example 2.1.

Consider $(Z_5 = \{0,1,2,3,4\}, +, \cdot)$ the ring of integers modulo 5, take $f : Z_5 \rightarrow [0,1]$;

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & ; x = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & ; x \in \{2,3\} \\ \frac{1}{4} & ; x = 4 \\ 0 & ; x = 0 \end{cases} ,$$

$Z_5(I) = \{0,1,2,3,4, I, 2I, 3I, 4I, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 1 + 3I, 1 + 4I, 2 + I, 2 + 2I, 2 + 3I, 2 + 4I, 3 + I, 3 + 2I, 3 + 3I, 3 + 4I, 4 + I, 4 + 2I, 4 + 3I, 4 + 4I\}$.

$$f_I(3 + 4I) = \min(f(3), f(4)) = \frac{1}{4}, \ f_I(1 + 2I) = \min(f(1), f(2)) = \frac{1}{2} .$$

By a similar approach, we can see:

$$f_I(1 + 4I) = f_I(2 + 4I) = \frac{1}{4}, f_I(0) = f_I(I) = f_I(2I) = f_I(3I) = f_I(4I) = 0, f_I(1 + 3I) = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$f_I(2 + I) = f_I(3 + I) = f_I(2) = f_I(3) = 1 \setminus 2, \text{ and so on.}$$

Therefore, $(Z_5(I))_{f_I} = \{(a + bI)_0, (a + bI)_1, (a + bI)_{\frac{1}{2}}, (a + bI)_{\frac{1}{4}}; \text{ for all } a, b \in Z_5\}$.

Definition 2.2.

An element $X = (a + bI)_{f_I(c+dI)}$ is called a minimal unit in the minimal two-fold neutrosophic ring $(Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ if and only if there exists:

$$Y = (m + nI)_{f_I(t+kI)} \in (Z_n(I))_{f_I}$$

such that:

$$X \circ Y = [(a + bI)(m + nI)]_{f_I[(c+dI)(t+kI)]} = 1_0.$$

Example 2.2.

Consider $Z_3 = \{0,1,2\}$, $Z_3(I) = \{0,1,2, I, 2I, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 2 + I, 2 + 2I\}$,

$$f: Z_3 \rightarrow [0,1] ; \begin{cases} f(0) = 0 \\ f(1) = 1 \\ f(2) = \frac{1}{2} \end{cases}, f_I: Z_n(I) \rightarrow [0,1]$$

such that:

$$f_I(0) = f_I(I) = f_I(2I) = f_I(1) = 0, f_I(1 + I) = 1, f_I(2) = 0, f_I(1 + 2I) = f_I(2 + I) =$$

$$f_I(2 + 2I) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Hence

$$(Z_3(I))_{f_I} = \left\{ 0_0, 0_1, 0_{\frac{1}{2}}, 1_0, 1_1, 1_{\frac{1}{2}}, I_0, I_1, I_{\frac{1}{2}}, (2I)_0, (2I)_1, (2I)_{\frac{1}{2}}, (1 + I)_0, (1 + I)_1, (1 + I)_{\frac{1}{2}}, (2 + I)_0, (2 + I)_1, (2 + I)_{\frac{1}{2}}, (1 + 2I)_0, (1 + 2I)_1, (1 + 2I)_{\frac{1}{2}}, (2 + 2I)_0, (2 + 2I)_1, (2 + 2I)_{\frac{1}{2}}, 2_0, 2_1, 2_{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}.$$

Theorem 2.1.

An element $X = (a + bI)_{f_I(m+nI)} \in (Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ is a minimal unit if and only if:

$$1] \gcd(a, n) = \gcd(a + b, n) = 1.$$

$$2] \exists t + kI \in Z_n(I) \text{ such that: } mt \equiv 0 \pmod{n} \quad \text{or} \quad (m + n)(t + k) - mt \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

Proof.

X is a minimal unit if and only if there exists $Y = (c + dI)_{f_I(t+kI)}$ with $X \circ Y = 1_0$, so that:

$$(a + bI)(c + dI) = 1 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} ac = 1 \\ ad + bc + bd = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} ac = 1 \\ (a + b)(c + d) - ac = 0 \end{cases} \\ \Rightarrow \begin{cases} ac = 1 \\ (a + b)(c + d) = ac = 1 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \gcd(a, n) = 1 \\ \gcd(a + b, n) = 1 \end{cases} .$$

On the other hand:

$$f_I[(m + nI)(t + kI)] = 0 \Rightarrow f_I[mt + I(mk + nt + nk)] = 0 \Rightarrow f_I[mt + I[(m + n)(t + k) - mt]] = 0, \text{ thus:}$$

$$f(mt) = 0 \text{ or } f[(m + n)(t + k) - mt] = 0,$$

hence

$$\begin{cases} mt = 0 \equiv 0(\text{mod } n) \\ \text{or} \\ (m + n)(t + k) - mt \equiv 0(\text{mod } n) \end{cases} .$$

Minimal units of $(Z_2(I))_{f_I}$:

$$Z_2 = \{0,1\}, Z_2(I) = \{0,1, I, 1 + I\}, \cup (Z_2) = \cup (Z_2(I)) = \{1\}.$$

For any $f: Z_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$,

we have:

$$f(0) = 0, f(1) = 1,$$

that is because (f) is a fuzzy mapping, hence: $f_I: Z_2(I) \rightarrow [0,1]$ with:

$$f_I(0) = f_I(1) = f_I(I) = 0, f_I(1 + I) = 1.$$

The minimal units of $(Z_2(I))_{f_I}$ are : $\{1_0, 1_1\}$, that is because $0 \cdot (1 + I) = 0$.

Remark 2.1.

For any two-fold minimal neutrosophic ring $(Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ and for any $m + nI \in Z_n(I)$, there exists

$0 \in Z_n(I)$ such that: $0 \cdot (m + nI) = 0$.

So that the minimal units of $Z_n(I)$ are:

$$M_u(Z_n(I)) = \{(a + bI)_x ; a + bI \in \cup (Z_n(I)) , x \in f(Z_n)\}$$

Minimal units of $Z_3(I)$, $Z_4(I)$:

$$Z_3 = \{0,1,2\}, Z_3(I) = \{0,1,2, I, 2I, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 2 + I, 2 + 2I\}, \\ \cup (Z_3) = \{1,2\}, \cup (Z_3(I)) = \{1,2,1 + I, 2 + 2I\}.$$

For any fuzzy mapping $f: Z_3 \rightarrow [0,1]$,

we have

$$f(0) = 0, f(1) = 1, f(2) \in]0,1[,$$

$$Z_4 = \{0,1,2,3\}, Z_4(I) = \{0,1,2,3, I, 2I, 3I, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 1 + 3I, 2 + I, 2 + 3I, 2 + 2I, 3 + I, 3 + 2I, 3 + 3I\},$$

$$\cup (Z_4) = \{1,3\}, \cup (Z_4(I)) = \{1,3,1 + 2I, 3 + 2I\}.$$

For any fuzzy mapping $f: Z_4(I) \rightarrow [0,1]$,

we have

$$f(0) = 0, f(1) = 1, f(2), f(3) \in]0,1[.$$

Minimal units of $(Z_3(I))_{f_I}$:

	$M_u(Z_3(I))_{f_I}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(2)}$
4	2_1
5	2_0
6	$2_{f(2)}$
7	$(1 + I)_0$
8	$(1 + I)_1$
9	$(1 + I)_{f(2)}$
10	$(2 + 2I)_0$
11	$(2 + 2I)_1$
12	$(2 + 2I)_{f(2)}$

Minimal units of $(Z_4(I))_{f_I}$ in the case of $f(2) = f(3)$:

	$M_u(Z_4(I))_{f_I}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(2)}$

4	3_0
5	3_1
6	$3_{f(2)}$
7	$(1 + 2I)_0$
8	$(1 + 2I)_1$
9	$(1 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
10	$(3 + 2I)_0$
11	$(3 + 2I)_1$
12	$(3 + 2I)_{f(2)}$

Minimal units of $(Z_4(I))_{f_I}$ in the case of $f(2) \neq f(3)$:

	$M_u(Z_4(I))_{f_I}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(2)}$
4	$1_{f(3)}$
5	3_0
6	3_1
7	$3_{f(2)}$
8	$3_{f(3)}$
9	$(3 + 2I)_0$
10	$(3 + 2I)_1$
11	$(3 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
12	$(3 + 2I)_{f(3)}$
13	$(1 + 2I)_0$
14	$(1 + 2I)_1$
15	$(1 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
16	$(1 + 2I)_{f(3)}$

Minimal units of $(Z_5(I))_{f_I}$:

$$Z_5 = \{0,1,2,3,4\}, Z_5(I) = \{0,1,2,3,4, I, 2I, 3I, 4I, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 1 + 3I, 1 + 4I, 2 + I, 2 + 2I, 2 + 3I, 2 + 4I, 3 + I, 3 + 2I, 3 + 3I, 3 + 4I, 4 + I, 4 + 2I, 4 + 3I, 4 + 4I\},$$

$$\cup (Z_5) = \{1,2,3,4\}, \cup (Z_5(I)) = \{1,2,3,4, 1 + I, 1 + 2I, 1 + 3I, 2 + I, 2 + 2I, 2 + 4I, 3 + I, 3 + 3I, 3 + 4I, 4 + 2I, 4 + 3I, 4 + 4I\}.$$

Minimal units of $(Z_5(I))_{f_I}$ in the case of $f(2) = f(3) = f(4)$:

	$M_u(Z_5(I))_{f_I}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(2)}$
4	2_0
5	2_1
6	$2_{f(2)}$
7	3_0
8	3_1
9	$3_{f(2)}$
10	4_0
11	4_1
12	$4_{f(2)}$
13	$(1 + I)_0$
14	$(1 + I)_1$
15	$(1 + I)_{f(2)}$
16	$(1 + 2I)_0$
17	$(1 + 2I)_1$

18	$(1 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
19	$(1 + 3I)_0$
20	$(1 + 3I)_1$
21	$(1 + 3I)_{f(2)}$
22	$(2 + I)_0$
23	$(2 + I)_1$
24	$(2 + I)_{f(2)}$
25	$(3 + I)_0$
26	$(3 + I)_1$
27	$(3 + I)_{f(2)}$
28	$(2 + 2I)_0$
29	$(2 + 2I)_1$
30	$(2 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
31	$(2 + 4I)_0$
32	$(2 + 4I)_1$
33	$(2 + 4I)_{f(2)}$
34	$(3 + 4I)_0$
35	$(3 + 4I)_1$
36	$(3 + 4I)_{f(2)}$
37	$(4 + 2I)_0$
38	$(4 + 2I)_1$
39	$(4 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
40	$(4 + 3I)_0$
41	$(4 + 3I)_1$
42	$(4 + 3I)_{f(2)}$
43	$(4 + 4I)_0$
44	$(4 + 4I)_1$
45	$(4 + 4I)_{f(2)}$

46	$(3 + 3I)_0$
47	$(3 + 3I)_1$
48	$(3 + 3I)_{f(2)}$

Minimal units of $(Z_5(I))_{f_1}$ in the case of $f(2) \neq f(3) \neq f(4)$:

	$M_u(Z_5(I))_{f_1}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(2)}$
4	$1_{f(3)}$
5	$1_{f(4)}$
6	2_0
7	2_1
8	$2_{f(2)}$
9	$2_{f(3)}$
10	$2_{f(4)}$
11	3_0
12	3_1
13	$3_{f(2)}$
14	$3_{f(3)}$
15	$3_{f(4)}$
16	4_0
17	4_1
18	$4_{f(2)}$
19	$4_{f(3)}$
20	$4_{f(4)}$
21	$(1 + I)_0$
22	$(1 + I)_1$

23	$(1 + I)_{f(2)}$
24	$(1 + I)_{f(3)}$
25	$(1 + I)_{f(4)}$
26	$(1 + 2I)_0$
27	$(1 + 2I)_1$
28	$(1 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
29	$(1 + 2I)_{f(3)}$
30	$(1 + 2I)_{f(4)}$
31	$(1 + 3I)_0$
32	$(1 + 3I)_1$
33	$(1 + 3I)_{f(2)}$
34	$(1 + 3I)_{f(3)}$
35	$(1 + 3I)_{f(4)}$
36	$(2 + I)_0$
37	$(2 + I)_1$
38	$(2 + I)_{f(2)}$
39	$(2 + I)_{f(3)}$
40	$(2 + I)_{f(4)}$
41	$(2 + 2I)_0$
42	$(2 + 2I)_1$
43	$(2 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
44	$(2 + 2I)_{f(3)}$
45	$(2 + 2I)_{f(4)}$
46	$(2 + 4I)_0$
47	$(2 + 4I)_1$
48	$(2 + 4I)_{f(2)}$
49	$(2 + 4I)_{f(3)}$
50	$(2 + 4I)_{f(4)}$

51	$(3 + I)_0$
52	$(3 + I)_1$
53	$(3 + I)_{f(2)}$
54	$(3 + I)_{f(3)}$
55	$(3 + I)_{f(4)}$
56	$(3 + 3I)_0$
57	$(3 + 3I)_1$
58	$(3 + 3I)_{f(2)}$
59	$(3 + 3I)_{f(3)}$
60	$(3 + 3I)_{f(4)}$
61	$(3 + 4I)_0$
62	$(3 + 4I)_1$
63	$(3 + 4I)_{f(2)}$
64	$(3 + 4I)_{f(3)}$
65	$(3 + 4I)_{f(4)}$
66	$(4 + 2I)_0$
67	$(4 + 2I)_1$
68	$(4 + 2I)_{f(2)}$
69	$(4 + 2I)_{f(3)}$
70	$(4 + 2I)_{f(4)}$
71	$(4 + 3I)_0$
72	$(4 + 3I)_1$
73	$(4 + 3I)_{f(2)}$
74	$(4 + 3I)_{f(3)}$
75	$(4 + 3I)_{f(4)}$
76	$(4 + 4I)_0$
77	$(4 + 4I)_1$
78	$(4 + 4I)_{f(2)}$

79	$(4 + 4I)_{f(3)}$
80	$(4 + 4I)_{f(4)}$

Minimal units of $(Z_5(I))_{f_I}$ in the case of $f(a) = f(b) \neq f(c)$; where $a, b, c \in \{2, 3, 4\}$:

	$M_u(Z_5(I))_{f_I}$
1	1_0
2	1_1
3	$1_{f(a)}$
4	$1_{f(c)}$
5	2_0
6	2_1
7	$2_{f(a)}$
8	$2_{f(c)}$
9	3_0
10	3_1
11	$3_{f(a)}$
12	$3_{f(c)}$
13	4_0
14	4_1
15	$4_{f(a)}$
16	$4_{f(c)}$
17	$(1 + I)_0$
18	$(1 + I)_1$
19	$(1 + I)_{f(a)}$
20	$(1 + I)_{f(c)}$
21	$(1 + 2I)_0$
22	$(1 + 2I)_1$

23	$(1 + 2I)_{f(a)}$
24	$(1 + 2I)_{f(c)}$
25	$(4 + 4I)_0$
26	$(4 + 4I)_1$
27	$(4 + 4I)_{f(a)}$
28	$(4 + 4I)_{f(c)}$
29	$(1 + 3I)_0$
30	$(1 + 3I)_1$
31	$(1 + 3I)_{f(a)}$
32	$(1 + 3I)_{f(c)}$
33	$(2 + I)_0$
34	$(2 + I)_1$
35	$(2 + I)_{f(a)}$
36	$(2 + I)_{f(c)}$
37	$(2 + 2I)_0$
38	$(2 + 2I)_1$
39	$(2 + 2I)_{f(a)}$
40	$(2 + 2I)_{f(c)}$
41	$(2 + 4I)_0$
42	$(2 + 4I)_1$
43	$(2 + 4I)_{f(a)}$
44	$(2 + 4I)_{f(c)}$
45	$(3 + I)_0$
46	$(3 + I)_1$
47	$(3 + I)_{f(a)}$
48	$(3 + I)_{f(c)}$
49	$(3 + 3I)_0$
50	$(3 + 3I)_1$

51	$(3 + 3I)_{f(a)}$
52	$(3 + 3I)_{f(c)}$
53	$(3 + 4I)_0$
54	$(3 + 4I)_1$
55	$(3 + 4I)_{f(a)}$
56	$(3 + 4I)_{f(c)}$
57	$(4 + 2I)_0$
58	$(4 + 2I)_1$
59	$(4 + 2I)_{f(a)}$
60	$(4 + 2I)_{f(c)}$
61	$(4 + 3I)_0$
62	$(4 + 3I)_1$
63	$(4 + 3I)_{f(a)}$
64	$(4 + 3I)_{f(c)}$

Conclusion

In this paper, we defined the concept of minimal units in finite two-fold finite neutrosophic rings modulo integers as a generalization of classical elements of the group of units of the mentioned neutrosophic rings. We applied our results to characterize all minimal units in the following two-fold neutrosophic rings $(Z_n(I))_{f_I}$ for $n \in \{2,3,4,5\}$.

In the future, we aim to classify all minimal units for higher orders cases $n \geq 6$.

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